

Local Government in Albania

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Albania: An Introduction

Elton Stafa, *NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Until 2015, urban and rural local self-governments in Albania were entrusted with symmetrical own, shared and delegated functions and responsibilities. Own functions were those functions over which local government units exercised full administrative, service, investment and regulatory authority. Public services related to infrastructure and utilities formed the core of exclusive functions of local governments in Albania. Shared functions included some generic maintenance responsibilities in the areas of pre-university education, primary health care and social protection. Delegated functions basically included all those central government functions the implementation of which was delegated to the local governments, through a specific law or bylaw. Unfortunately, the symmetrical decentralization of responsibilities to both urban and rural local governments, in a context of extreme territorial fragmentation and insufficient human, material and financial resources have led to significant disparities in terms of access to and quality of services.⁹

In late 2015, the Parliament of Albania adopted a new Law on Local Self-Government. This new law aims at harmonizing Albania's local government legal framework with the TAR and consolidating and expanding the authority of the 61 newly created local governments to perform new services in accordance with the provisions of the new National Cross Cutting Strategy for Decentralization and Local Government.¹⁰

Local governments in Albania perform own and delegated functions and competences, which are decentralized in a symmetrical manner.¹¹ Local Self-Governments have full authority to *regulate* and *administer* the exercise of their own functions in an autonomous manner. The ability to regulate refers to the right to establish general and normative rules of conduct and binding standards in compliance with the law. The ability to administer refers to the right to plan, finance and organize the exercise of a function. Although they enjoy autonomy, when performing their tasks, local governments should also respect regional and national policies. In fact, in cases of national interests or to ensure qualitative services, the national government may impose specific norms and standards, also on own local functions. In the latter cases, the law¹² requires that the national government provides the necessary financial support.

⁹ Law no 8652/2000 on the Organisation and Functioning of Local Governments.

¹⁰ Government of Albania, 'National Crosscutting Strategy for Decentralization and Local Governance 2015-2020' (adopted by Decision of the Council of Ministers no 691 of 29 July 2015).

¹¹ Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government, Art 21.

¹² *ibid*, Art 22.

Local self-governments have own responsibilities in the core public services and public infrastructure; education; social protection; culture, recreation and sports; environmental protection; agriculture, rural development, forests and pastures, nature and biodiversity; local economic development; and public order and safety. Obviously, the degree of political and administrative powers decentralized to local governments vary from function to function.

From the functional responsibility perspective, the new Law on Local Self-Government brought a number of novelties: (i) the elimination of shared functions – which meant an immediate transformation of the previous shared functions into exclusive functions. The rationale for this choice was to reduce confusion and vagueness over local government responsibilities. Indeed, to some degree, the concrete ‘shares’ of responsibilities of the national and local governments on ‘shared functions’ were never fully clarified. This made local governments exclusively responsible for maintaining, operating and building new schools and health and social service centers – the responsibility over which was previously shared with local governments. Unfortunately, this change was not accompanied by any increase in intergovernmental transfers. Local governments responsibilities changed overnight without a significant increase in their revenue sources¹³; (ii) the decentralization of a number of new and costly functions to local governments, including paying teachers in kindergartens and preschools and support staff in all levels of pre-university education; the regulation and administration of fire protection; irrigation and drainage; agricultural counselling; the maintenance of rural roads (previously performed by the regions); the establishment, regulation and administration of social services, including day care centers for disadvantaged groups; social housing; and the establishment of a social fund; etc. Unlike the transfer of the ‘shared’ functions, the transfer of these new responsibilities in 2016 was accompanied by the introduction of a specific earmarked grant, broken down per function and municipality by the respective line ministry.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Sources

Legal Documents:

Law no 8652/2000 on the Organization and Functioning of Local Governments

Law no 115/2014 on the Administrative-Territorial Division of Local Government Units in the Republic of Albania

Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government

Government of Albania, ‘National Crosscutting Strategy for Decentralization and Local Governance 2015-2020’ (adopted by Decision of the Council of Ministers no 691 of 29 July 2015)

¹³ Tony Levitas and Elton Stafa, ‘Financing the New Own Functions of Local Governments in Albania’ (USAID 2018) <<https://www.plgp.al/financing-the-new-own-functions-of-local-governments-in-albania/>>.

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Levitas T and Stafa E, 'Financing the New Own Functions of Local Governments in Albania' (USAID 2018) <<https://www.plgp.al/financing-the-new-own-functions-of-local-governments-in-albania/>>

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